

Measuring Neutron Flux Gradient: Design, Prototyping, and Deployment of a Novel Sensor at the PUR-1 Research Reactor

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ABSTRACT

Accurate characterization of spatial flux variations near reactor-core boundaries supports advanced diagnostics and inverse methods for reconstructing in-core power distributions from limited measurements. High-spatial-resolution flux mapping has been demonstrated using activation dosimetry and miniature detectors, and position-sensitive systems can resolve one-dimensional gradients in certain configurations. However, these approaches do not typically yield a compact, co-located estimate of the transverse flux-gradient vector from co-located differential measurements suited for boundary-condition use. This paper reports the design and proof-of-concept demonstration of a four-element (“quadrupole-geometry”) sensor that estimates the two in-plane components of the neutron-flux gradient. A prototype uses copper activation wires with post-irradiation gamma spectrometry, enabling rapid evaluation without online electronics. The device was deployed at the PUR-1 research reactor, where repeated irradiations produced reproducible differential responses consistent with a nonzero boundary gradient. Comparisons with MCNP6 calculations show qualitative agreement in gradient orientation and axial trends, while quantitative accuracy is limited by copper activation sensitivity, decay-time constraints, and experimental handling and counting uncertainties. These results motivate a second-generation design based on higher-sensitivity activation materials (e.g., gold), improved metrology, and more explicit uncertainty quantification, providing an experimental basis for quadrupole-based gradient estimation as a boundary measurement for non-intrusive neutron-field monitoring.

Keywords: Neutron flux gradient, Directional detector, Quadrupole sensor, Ex-core instrumentation, Advanced Reactors.

1. INTRODUCTION

Reliable knowledge of the neutron-flux distribution inside a reactor core is central to power monitoring, validation of neutronics models, and irradiation experiments. In commercial Light-Water Reactors, core surveillance typically relies on dense networks of in-core and ex-core detectors to reconstruct the spatial power distribution with high accuracy [1]. Modern designs deploy dozens of in-core self-powered neutron detector (SPND) strings distributed across the core, with multiple detectors per string to sample the axial power shape. Advanced reactors and microreactors, however, operate in more compact and demanding environments where elevated temperatures, corrosive coolants, and limited access reduce the lifetime and reliability of conventional in-core instrumentation. These systems also involve higher local neutron fluxes ($\sim 10^{13}$ - 10^{15} n·cm⁻²s⁻¹) and large cycle-integrated fluences ($\sim 10^{22}$ n·cm⁻²), which can further degrade signal integrity and mechanical alignment. These constraints motivate approaches that infer in-core quantities from measurements made at or near the core boundary, where instrumentation is generally more feasible and maintainable.

A broad set of techniques can characterize spatial flux variations, ranging from activation dosimetry to miniature and position-sensitive detectors in research reactors. Importantly, beyond flux magnitude

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alone, the flux gradient can carry additional directional information about spatial changes in the field. Pázsit highlighted that access to flux-gradient information can substantially increase the information content available for core-monitoring and inverse diagnostics, motivating detector concepts that can resolve directional components of neutron propagation [2]. The present work targets this boundary-measurement need by estimating the local transverse flux-gradient vector from co-located differential measurements. Using a four-element “quadrupole” arrangement, we compare flux-proportional responses from opposing sensing elements to estimate the in-plane components $\partial\phi/\partial x$ and $\partial\phi/\partial y$ under a local linear-gradient approximation. Importantly, the device measures flux-proportional responses at four nearby locations, from which a gradient estimate can be computed. As a first experimental evaluation, the quadrupole geometry was implemented using copper activation wires and post-irradiation gamma spectrometry, enabling rapid evaluation of differential response and repeatability without online electronics. The prototype is deployed at Purdue University Reactor Number One (PUR-1) and results are compared to MCNP simulations. The measurements exhibit reproducible differential signals and show qualitative agreement in gradient orientation and axial trends, while quantitative accuracy is limited by copper activation sensitivity and by experimental handling, segmentation, and counting uncertainties. These findings motivate a clear path toward improved fidelity through higher-sensitivity activation materials.

2. REVIEW OF CONCEPTUAL DESIGNS AND IMPLEMENTATIONS FOR NEUTRON FLUX GRADIENT DETECTORS

Neutron flux gradients provide information beyond flux magnitude by encoding the direction and local spatial rate of change of the neutron field. This directional content is valuable for monitoring and inverse problems that rely on boundary measurements, because gradients strengthen observability of spatial perturbations compared with flux-only data. In a seminal study [2], Pázsit demonstrated that higher angular moments of the neutron flux contain directional information that can enhance the observability of neutron fields in multiplying media. Pázsit also identified the principal barrier to experimental implementation: the absence of detectors capable of directly measuring neutron-flux gradient components under reactor conditions. In practice, “flux-gradient measurements” are typically obtained through co-located differential sampling: flux-proportional responses are recorded at two (or more) nearby locations and combined using finite-difference relations to estimate components of $\nabla\phi$. This is distinct from a direct measurement of neutron current. A current density may be derived from a gradient estimate only under an assumed constitutive closure (e.g., diffusion-theory Fick’s law) and an appropriate transport coefficient.

2.1. Dedicated gradient-detector concepts

A representative dedicated concept is the “neutron flux gradient detector” proposed in [3], which uses four miniature sensing elements arranged in a rectangular pattern such that opposing elements provide differential signals along two orthogonal directions. This geometry enables estimation of the two in-plane Cartesian components of the flux-gradient vector from a compact, co-located assembly. The work provides a clear design template for gradient sensing—symmetric placement, short baselines, and differential readout—while highlighting practical sensitivities to spacing, alignment, and local spectral/field heterogeneity that can bias finite-difference estimates.

2.2. Directional inference from distributed detectors

Work in radiation-source localization provides a related precedent for extracting directional information from differential count-rate patterns, even when the primary objective is not flux-gradient measurement. At Argonne National Laboratory, Vilim and Klann developed the RadTrac concept, in which spatially distributed detectors feed a processing unit that continuously estimates the most probable source location using statistical inference applied to measured count-rate differences (i.e., gradient-like information) [4]. Tests with a small set of fixed detectors demonstrated real-time tracking of weak sources from reproducible differential count-rate patterns. While developed for source localization rather than reactor boundary monitoring, this work underscores that differential measurements enhance directional observability and motivates compact, co-located geometries for extracting local gradient information.

2.3. Highly localized miniature detectors enabling gradient inference

In parallel with dedicated gradient geometries, substantial progress has been made in miniature in-core neutron detectors that provide localized scalar-flux measurements at millimeter-to-centimeter scales. Although these systems are not necessarily designed as “gradient detectors” per se, their spatial resolution enables gradient inference when measurements are taken at multiple nearby locations. Two examples emphasized by the reviewers demonstrate this capability in research-reactor environments. Vitullo et al. reported highly localized azimuthal measurements in the CROCUS reactor as part of a validation effort for high-fidelity neutronics calculations, illustrating that localized spatial sampling can resolve fine flux variations relevant to gradient inference [5]. Brunetto et al. demonstrated high-resolution thermal-flux measurements in the SUR-100 facility using miniature fiber-coupled scintillators, showing that compact detector tips can achieve centimeter-wise spatial resolution in experimental channels [6]. Together, these studies establish that localized detector technologies can support gradient estimation through close spatial sampling, while also underscoring the need for careful treatment of positioning, repeatability, and uncertainty to obtain quantitative gradients.

2.4. Positioning of the present work

The present work extends prior quadrupole and directional-detector concepts by implementing a radiation-tolerant, activation-based prototype that enables an offline proof-of-concept demonstration without online electronics. This approach focuses on establishing repeatable differential responses under reactor constraints while identifying the dominant practical contributors to gradient-estimation uncertainty (e.g., segmentation, alignment, counting statistics, and handling). The results provide a basis for design improvements—such as higher-sensitivity activation materials and improved metrology—and for subsequent extensions toward online implementations.

3. CANDIDATE TECHNOLOGIES FOR QUADRUPOLE DETECTORS

The proposed quadrupole detector retains four identical sensing elements arranged orthogonally around a central axis—two along x and two along y —to estimate the magnitude and direction of the local transverse flux-gradient vector. Differential responses from opposing sensors provide the two in-plane components of $\nabla\phi$ through a local finite-difference approximation (Eq.1),

$$\nabla\phi \approx \frac{1}{2d} [(\phi_A - \phi_C)\hat{x} + (\phi_B - \phi_D)\hat{y}] \quad (1)$$

where d is the half-distance between opposing sensors, and ϕ_i denotes the flux-proportional response at each sensing element, and \hat{x}, \hat{y} are unit vectors along the two measurement axes. Realizing a reactor-qualified quadrupole detector requires sensing technologies that combine radiation tolerance, geometric precision, and calibration stability over multi-year exposure periods. Accordingly, concepts developed for lower-flux environments may require adaptation for long-term reactor deployment. The selection of sensing technology is therefore driven by achievable sensitivity, lifetime, and integration complexity; the main options are summarized below.

- **Activation-based implementations (foils/wires).** Activation dosimetry offers excellent radiation tolerance and simple packaging, making it attractive for early demonstrations of quadrupole differential behavior under reactor constraints. It is inherently off-line and its quantitative accuracy depends on handling/segmentation, counting statistics, decay logistics, and geometric alignment. Nevertheless, activation-based prototypes provide a practical path to validate geometry, establish repeatability, and identify dominant uncertainty sources before pursuing online implementations.
- **Fiber-coupled miniature scintillators.** Miniature scintillation tips coupled to optical fibers enable compact geometries while relocating sensitive electronics away from the high-temperature/high-fluence region. They can support near-real-time measurements and tight baselines but require careful control of channel matching and drift (radiation-induced optical changes, temperature dependence, and gamma sensitivity). For quadrupole use, the key design need is preserving relative channel accuracy to avoid bias in differential signals.

- **Gas-filled detectors and SPNDs.** Gas-filled detectors (including fission chambers) and SPNDs offer favorable robustness and long-term stability [7]. Their limitations for quadrupole deployment are typically practical: packaging and footprint for a co-located four-channel assembly, routing constraints, and—especially for SPNDs—response-time characteristics that may restrict use to steady or slowly varying gradients. Among available emitters, Rhodium SPNDs offer absolute measurement capability with proven radiation tolerance up to 10^{18} n·cm⁻² and diameters as small as 1.6 mm [8]. Large-scale deployment, however, introduces significant cabling and alignment complexity. For a reactor the size of PUR-1, mapping the flux and gradient over 12 cm × 12 cm peripheral segments would require roughly 80 quadrupole assemblies—320 individual leads in total—necessitating custom cladding geometries and careful routing.
- **Optical-Fiber Detectors.** Optical fibers offer a compact, cable-efficient alternative to metallic sensors, providing immunity to electromagnetic interference and ease of installation around reactor structures. Their sensing principle can exploit radiation-induced attenuation (RIA) or fluence-dependent spectral shifts in back-scattered light. In an intensity-based approach, an optical time-domain reflectometer (OTDR) launches short infrared pulses and samples the back-scattered signal to localize attenuation changes along the fiber, enabling inference of incremental fluence and thus average neutron flux with centimeter-scale spatial resolution [9]. In a shift-based approach, spectral analysis detects small wavelength displacements proportional to accumulated fluence, although reported sensitivities can be limited (e.g., ~1 nm shifts only after fast-neutron fluences on the order of 10^{20} n·cm⁻²) [10]. Both methods require careful calibration of RIA or wavelength-shift response and can entail significant instrumentation cost, though multiplexing multiple fibers through optical switching can mitigate the need for dedicated readout channels.

4. QUADRUPOLE DETECTOR PROTOTYPING AND EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

Among the evaluated options, Rhodium SPNDs and optical-fiber-based sensors emerged as the most suitable candidates for quadrupole deployment—the former for their proven durability and calibration stability, the latter for their compactness and simplified signal routing. However, their fabrication cost and calibration complexity make them less suitable for a first-generation prototype. An activation-based quadrupole prototype was collaboratively designed and fabricated by ANL and Purdue University during July–August 2025 and subsequently installed in the PUR-1. These results inform a clear technology roadmap toward higher-sensitivity activation materials and, ultimately, toward online quadrupole implementations where deployment conditions permit.

4.1. Experimental Demonstration at PUR-1

The prototype comprised four identical oxygen-free copper wires (≈ 0.15 cm diameter, ≈ 60 cm length) mounted vertically in an empty PUR-1 fuel-assembly channel and arranged symmetrically in a transverse quadrupole layout. Opposing wire pairs provide finite-difference estimates of the two in-plane components of the local flux gradient, consistent with Eq. (1). The wire spacing $2d$ was selected as a sensitivity–bias compromise: smaller baselines reduce differential signal relative to counting/handling uncertainty, whereas larger baselines weaken the local linear-gradient assumption while also being constrained by the channel envelope and alignment tolerances. To maintain the prescribed geometry during irradiation, a dedicated positioning and stabilization fixture fixed the wire locations along the active length. The assembly included a central positioning adapter, upper and lower stabilizers, and an external aluminum container for handling and protection (Figure 1). The center-to-center spacing between opposing wires was $2d = 0.6$ cm, set by the channel envelope and adapter geometry (Figure 2a). Components were fabricated from aluminum and radiation-tolerant polymer to limit perturbation and to simplify handling; alignment was verified prior to installation.

The quadrupole was deployed at the C4 ex-core position, selected because prior activation characterization indicated it provided the highest measurable flux among candidate locations—an important practical requirement for the present Cu activation approach (Figure 2b). Copper was selected to enable a fast, low-cost, activation-based demonstration of differential response using readily available materials and straightforward post-irradiation counting, recognizing that its relatively small

capture cross section and the use of the 511 keV annihilation peak limit achievable precision and motivate the next design iteration with higher-sensitivity materials (e.g., Au).

Figure 1. Quadrupole positioning and stabilization hardware used to hold four copper activation wires during irradiation.

Figure 2. (a) Quadrupole adapter drawing showing the sensing-element spacing (dimensions in cm). (b) Schematic of the PUR-1 core configuration (fueled lattice and reflector region) showing the C4 irradiation position and the x-y coordinate convention used for transverse gradient reconstruction.

4.2. Irradiation, gamma counting, and flux inference

The thermal neutron flux at each wire position was inferred from the measured activation counts using Eq. 2,

$$\phi_0 = \frac{G \cdot \lambda_{64}}{\epsilon \cdot N_{63} \cdot \sigma_{eff} \cdot (1 - e^{-\lambda_{64}t_0}) \cdot e^{-\lambda_{64}t_w} \cdot (1 - e^{-\lambda_{64}t_c})} \quad (2)$$

where G is the background-corrected gross count, $\lambda_{64} = 1.5159 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ is the decay constant of ^{64}Cu , ϵ accounts for detector and geometric efficiencies, N_{63} is the number of ^{63}Cu atoms, σ_{eff} is the effective thermal capture cross section, t_0 is the irradiation time, t_w is the cooling/transfer time between irradiation and counting, and t_c is the live counting time in the high-purity germanium (HPGe) detector.

The effective cross section σ_{eff} was evaluated using the Westcott formalism, following ASTM E261-16 and ASTM E262-17. In this framework, departures from ideal $1/v$ behavior and epithermal contributions are captured through a correction to the 2200 m/s reference cross section (σ_0). Accordingly, we defined $\sigma_{eff} = \sigma_0 (g + r s)$, where g is the Westcott g -factor, r is the epithermal-to-thermal flux ratio, and s is a spectral-shape parameter associated with the low-energy end of the epithermal contribution.

The Westcott convention was adopted because the quadrupole geometry does not readily support multi-foil spectral characterization or cadmium-ratio measurements at each sensing element, and because it provides a practical, semi-empirical basis for flux inference and model benchmarking when direct spectral constraints are limited.

The reactor operated at steady-state power while the copper-wire array was irradiated for a duration selected using a timing-parameter optimization algorithm. The algorithm chose irradiation, cooling, and counting intervals that maximize net counts while targeting low counting-statistics uncertainty, accounting for activation buildup, decay, and detector dead time. After irradiation, the wires were segmented into 2.5 cm sections, and their induced activities were measured using HPGe gamma-ray spectrometry. The dominant experimental limitations for the present copper implementation were (i) the short 12.7 h half-life of ^{64}Cu , (ii) manual handling and repositioning of the 96 wire segments during counting, and (iii) the relatively small capture cross section of ^{63}Cu . Despite these limitations, reproducible differential activity patterns were observed among the four wires, indicating sensitivity to spatial gradient variations.

4.3. Numerical Modeling and Validation

To interpret the activation measurements and provide a physics-based reference for comparison, a detailed MCNP6 model of the PUR-1 core and the deployed quadrupole assembly was used [11]. Figures 3 and 4 present the measured and simulated axial profiles and the corresponding reconstructed transverse vectors, respectively. Each copper wire was represented explicitly and subdivided axially into 63 cells (1 cm each) to resolve variations along the active length. Simulations were performed with $4 \cdot 10^9$ neutron histories to obtain converged axial response profiles over the 0–0.1 MeV energy range. To ensure a consistent experiment–simulation comparison, the 1-cm MCNP6 axial profiles were re-binned into 2.5-cm interval to match the experimental wire segmentation, and the simulated responses were processed with the same finite-difference relations used for the measurements to obtain transverse gradient components at the same elevations.

Figure 3. Comparison of simulated and measured neutron flux distributions along the copper wires.

A small fraction of wire segments were excluded using an objective criterion applied uniformly across the dataset. A segment was flagged as an outlier if (i) its deviation from both adjacent segments exceeded 3σ relative to the local axial trend (estimated with a moving-window fit), or (ii) it introduced a localized discontinuity in the numerically evaluated axial gradient, identified by an abrupt sign change across that segment. These exclusions are consistent with the HPGe counting configuration, since the full-energy-peak efficiency is sensitive to segment placement relative to the detector endcap

(standoff distance, centering, and tilt); small repositioning differences can therefore introduce isolated biases during high-throughput counting. Uncertainty bands for the measured flux and reconstructed gradients in Figures 3 and 4 include counting-statistics uncertainty and, where applicable, efficiency and timing contributions (nuclear-data uncertainties were not propagated). To identify the dominant experimental contributors, we computed the fractional standard error of each quantity entering the flux calculation and treated terms with percentage errors exceeding 0.01% as potentially non-negligible.

In Figure 3, July 2025 measurements are shown in blue, excluded outliers in red, and MCNP6 predictions as yellow curves with statistical uncertainties. The excluded points were associated with localized counting/handling irregularities (e.g., minor positioning differences during HPGe measurements) that produced inconsistencies relative to neighboring segments and repeated counts. Figure 4 compares reconstructed and MCNP6-derived transverse flux-gradient vectors at four axial elevations along the quadrupole axis (top left, clockwise: 31.0, 53.5, 61.0, and 56.0 cm). Vectors are plotted as $\nabla\phi$ (directed inward toward the core), the dashed outline denotes the core boundary, and shaded bands indicate uncertainties for both simulation and experiment. The reconstructed gradients show similar orientations and comparable magnitudes across elevations, supporting the use of a quadrupole finite-difference geometry to extract boundary gradient information under the present experimental conditions.

Figure 4. Comparison of MCNP6-predicted and experimentally reconstructed transverse neutron flux-gradient vectors at four axial elevations along the quadrupole axis.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented the design and fabrication of a quadrupole-geometry prototype intended to estimate the directional components of the transverse neutron-flux gradient near a reactor core boundary. The activation-based prototype was deployed at Purdue University's PUR-1 research reactor, where repeated irradiations yielded reproducible differential responses between opposing sensing elements. Comparisons with MCNP6 simulations showed overall consistency in axial trends and reconstructed vector orientation, supporting the feasibility of extracting boundary gradient information from co-located differential measurements, while also highlighting practical limitations associated with copper activation, timing logistics, and counting/handling uncertainties.

Based on these findings, a second-generation quadrupole prototype using gold activation wires is planned to improve sensitivity and reduce decay-related counting losses. Future iterations will also evaluate online implementations (e.g., Rh-SPNDs or fiber-coupled modules) within the same quadrupole geometry to enable real-time measurements under reactor operating conditions. The modular housing developed for this study provides a convenient platform for these follow-on configurations.

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